

MULTIMEDIA PRODUCTS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE*Nurabayeva N.**Shakarim State University of Semey, Semey, Kazakhstan, Master student***Abstract**

The use of multimedia technologies plays a significant role in modern language teaching. The use of electronic dictionaries, encyclopedias, interactive textbooks and manuals, games, Internet resources, simulators, electronic presentations etc. makes it possible to increase the efficiency of material acquisition. Some Internet resources which play a significant role in the modernization of education are described in the given article.

Keywords: multimedia technologies, learning a foreign language, Internet resources.

Multimedia technologies are designed to provide a higher-quality level of assimilation of the studied material and increase the effectiveness of learning in general [1].

Multimedia is interactive systems that work with static images and moving video, animated computer graphics and text, speech and high-quality sound. Multimedia means are a set of hardware and software tools that allow a person to communicate with a computer using a variety of natural environments: sound, video, graphics, texts, animation [2].

Translated from English, “multimedia” is a multi-component environment that allows you to use text, graphics, video and animation in a dialogue mode and thereby expands the scope of a computer in teaching [3].

Traditionally, the process of learning a foreign language involves the transmission of theoretical information and the development of the skills necessary for successful communication within the discipline. Multimedia can have a positive impact on several aspects of the learning process. In the classroom environment, the teacher does not always have the opportunity to give due attention to each learner, which leads to a loss of motivation to learn and a lowering of knowledge, skills and abilities. Multimedia can be applied in the context of a variety of learning styles and can be understood by a variety of people: some choose to learn by reading, others by listening, others by watching videos, etc.

The use of multimedia in foreign language classes allows for a personal-oriented approach, promotes individualization and differentiation of education, i.e., reinforces the activities of students, increase interest in the subject and enable each student to organize independent work with interest in the subject matter and enables each student to organize his or her own work in accordance with his or her age, psychological characteristics and language proficiency. “While working with multimedia tools, students can influence their own learning process by adapting it to their individual abilities and preferences. They study exactly the material they are interested in, repeat the study as many times as they need, which promotes a more correct perception” [4].

One of the main benefits of multimedia is that it enables students to engage in a variety of learning activities by providing various ways to broaden their vocabulary and familiarize them with new expressions, improving the memory of the language constructions being studied and the relationships between these constructions, training of certain skills.

Use of audio and video materials (songs, educational films with different thematic focus, news programmes, TV broadcasts, advertisements, etc. in classes) also promotes the diversity of student activities and allows the artificial creation of a language environment, immersing the students in the reality of another country and thus develop not only a linguistic but also a socio-cultural competence. Multimedia technologies allow the student not only to be a spectator of the finished educational material, but also to participate in its creation, transformation, operational use.

Various Internet resources play a significant role in the modernization of education. First, these resources implement the principle of authenticity, which is important in modern foreign language teaching. The use of un-adapted texts from foreign newspapers and magazines, various websites and other sources enables the learning of the language in its modern functioning. Wide opportunities for effective language acquisition are provided by chat rooms, various types of Internet telephony (Skype), “instant messaging” (ICQ, Qip), “social diaries” (Livejournal) and “social networks” (Facebook, Vkontakte), as well as videoconferencing (Zoom, Google Meets). These means of communication allow to carry out “live” communication with native speakers in a situation “here and now”. It also contributes to the immersion of pupils in a natural language environment without additional material and time costs and to the development of a communicative competence.

It is important to note that Internet resources help to make the process of learning a foreign language more entertaining, as they enable teachers to vary the ways in which information is presented and to make the training practically directed. Moreover, because Internet technology is one of the most important sources of information in modern society, when students are included in their studies, they acquire the necessary skills to use Internet resources. The introduction of computer technologies in the educational process helps to improve not only the students, but also the teachers, i.e., gives the opportunity to exchange methodical experience with national and foreign colleagues. The use of multimedia tools also benefits from the fact that they optimize the control and self-control system, thus facilitating the work of the teacher as well as developing the autonomy of the learners. Through the use of computer tests, students are able to independently monitor the level of learning and, if necessary, repeat it.

The integration of multimedia tools in the education process contributes to savings in the use of materials by teachers and educational institutions. The availability of computerized classrooms, multimedia tools, interactive panels and other multimedia tools reduces the need for print publications and additional distribution materials.

It should be mentioned that the introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process can be both positive (contributing to learning efficiency) and negative (using multimedia tools incorrectly or inappropriately). It is obvious that the problem of appropriate and justified informatization of education must be addressed in an integrated manner. There are two possible ways of introducing multimedia into the educational process. The first is that “such tools are included in the learning process as “supporting” tools in traditional methods of education system” [4]. In this case, multimedia resources are a means of intensifying learning, individualizing learning and partially automating the work of teachers in accounting, measuring and evaluating students' knowledge.

Implementation of multimedia resources under track 2 “results in a change in the content of education, a revision of the methods and forms of the organization of the educational process, the construction of holistic courses based on the use of the content of resources in individual educational disciplines” [4]. Knowledge, skills and skills are not seen as an objective but as a means of developing the learner's personality. The use of multimedia technologies would be justified if full learning without them was impossible or difficult. When using multimedia means in the method of teaching a foreign language, it seems advisable to introduce them as “supporting”, rather than as primary language, since the specificity of teaching a foreign language im-

plies a key role of the teacher, who does not only manage the learning process, but also is a direct participant in it.

Conclusion.

The new generation is likely to study with new technologies. It is becoming hard to use traditional methods and tools to teach students of these days. Moreover, with the pandemic spread all over the world and transfer of all educational institutions into online learning format, the new technology is gaining its popularity. The role of multimedia in interactive textbooks is ambiguous. The feedback in this case does not go beyond the parameters “correct-wrong”. The interactive factor, the element of surprise, the non-standard answer, the reduction of meaning is completely excluded, which again underlines the necessity of the teacher's participation in foreign language training.

References

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